

On $S_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$ and $V_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$ -summability

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Abstract

In this paper, we introduce $S_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$ -summability and $V_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$ -summability in gradual normed linear spaces abbreviated as *GNLS*. We present examples to support definitions and investigate some relations between the spaces of such summability methods in gradual

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1 Introduction and Preliminaries

A generalized method of summability, called statistical convergence, was given in [3] using natural density of subsets of \mathbb{N} and further examined by several authors including Fridy [5, 6], Fridy and Orhan [7] Connor [2], Mursaleen [9] etc.

“For $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$, the natural density of A is denoted by $\delta(A)$ and is given by

$$\delta(A) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} |\{a \leq n : a \in A\}|_c$$

where $|\{\cdot\}|_c$ denotes the cardinality of the enclosed set”

“A sequence $t = (t_k)$ of numbers is said to converge statistically to a number t_0 if for each $\epsilon > 0$, $\delta(A(\epsilon)) = 0$ where $A(\epsilon) = \{k \in \mathbb{N} : |t_k - t_0| \geq \epsilon\}$. This is equivalent to writing

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} |\{k \in \mathbb{N} : |t_k - t_0| \geq \epsilon\}|_c = 0.$$

In this case, we will write $S - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} t_k = t_0$ or simply $t_k \rightarrow t_0(S)$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$.”

Mursaleen [9] gave an interesting generalization of statistical convergence, called “ λ -statistical convergence”, as follows.

“Let $\lambda = (\lambda_n)$ be a non-decreasing sequence of positive numbers with $\lambda_n \rightarrow \infty$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. A sequence $t = (t_k)$ of numbers is said to be λ -statistical convergent to a number t_0 if for each $\epsilon > 0$,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\lambda_n} |\{k \in I_n : |t_k - t_0| \geq \epsilon\}|_c = 0;$$

where $I_n = [n - \lambda_n + 1, n]$. In this case, we write $S_\lambda - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} t_k = t_0$ or $t_k \rightarrow t_0(S_\lambda)$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$.”

Kostryrko et al. [8] gave a different generalization of statistical convergence using ideals. We next give the terminology of ideals and related convergence. “For any nonempty set X , let $\mathcal{P}(X)$ denote the power set of X . A family of subsets $\mathcal{I} \subset \mathcal{P}(X)$ is said to be ideal in X if and only if (i) $\emptyset \in \mathcal{I}$; (ii) for each $A_1, A_2 \in \mathcal{I}$, $A_1 \cup A_2 \in \mathcal{I}$; (iii) for each $A_1 \in \mathcal{I}$ and $A_2 \subseteq A_1$ implies $A_2 \in \mathcal{I}$. Moreover, A family of subsets $\mathcal{F} \subset \mathcal{P}(X)$ is called a filter on X if and only if (i) $\emptyset \notin \mathcal{F}$; (ii) for each $A_1, A_2 \in \mathcal{F}$, $A_1 \cap A_2 \in \mathcal{F}$; (iii) for each $A_1 \in \mathcal{F}$ and $A_1 \subseteq A_2$ implies $A_2 \in \mathcal{F}$. An ideal \mathcal{I} is called nontrivial if $\mathcal{I} \neq \emptyset$ and $X \notin \mathcal{I}$. The filter $\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{I}) = \{X - A : A \in \mathcal{I}\}$ is called the filter associated with the ideal \mathcal{I} . A non-trivial ideal $\mathcal{I} \subset \mathcal{P}(X)$ is called an admissible ideal in X if and only if $\{\{x\} : x \in X\} \in \mathcal{I}$. Furthermore, an admissible ideal \mathcal{I} is said to satisfy condition (AP), if for every countable family of mutually disjoint sets $\{P_j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ from \mathcal{I} , there exists a countable family of sets $\{Q_j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ in \mathcal{I} s.t the symmetric difference $P_j \Delta K_j$ is finite for all $j \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\bigcup_{j=1}^{\infty} K_j \in \mathcal{I}$. For a non-trivial admissible ideal $\mathcal{I} \subset \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{N})$, A real sequence $t = (t_k)$ is said to be \mathcal{I} -convergent to t_0 if for each $\epsilon > 0$, the set $A(\epsilon) = \{k \in \mathbb{N} : |t_k - t_0| \leq \epsilon\} \in \mathcal{I}$. In this case, we write $\mathcal{I} - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} t_k = t_0$.”

Fortin et al. [4] gave a new approach in fuzzy set theory by defining gradual real numbers to analyze uncertainty and vagueness in complex data. They considered fuzzy intervals as crisp sets of entities instead of fuzzy sets. These numbers have wide applications in the examination of fuzzy intervals and fuzzy optimization theory.

“A gradual real number \tilde{n} is an assignment function $A_{\tilde{n}} : (0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. Let $\mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R})$ denote the set of all gradual real numbers. In addition, any $\tilde{n} \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R})$

is said to be positive if $A_{\tilde{n}}(\eta) \geq 0$ for $\eta \in (0, 1]$. Let $\mathcal{G}^*(\mathbb{R})$ denote the set of such numbers.

For $\tilde{n}_1, \tilde{n}_2 \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R})$, $\tilde{n}_1 \circ \tilde{n}_2 \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R})$ is defined by

$$A_{\tilde{n}_1 \circ \tilde{n}_2}(\eta) = A_{\tilde{n}_1}(\eta) \circ A_{\tilde{n}_2}(\eta) \text{ for } \eta \in (0, 1];$$

where $A_{\tilde{n}_1 \circ \tilde{n}_2}$ denotes the assignment function of $\tilde{n}_1 \circ \tilde{n}_2 \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R})$.

Similarly, $\tilde{n}_1 + \tilde{n}_2$ and $c\tilde{n}_1$ for $\tilde{n}_1, \tilde{n}_2 \in \mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R})$ and $c \in \mathbb{R}$ are defined by

$$A_{\tilde{n}_1 + \tilde{n}_2}(\eta) = A_{\tilde{n}_1}(\eta) + A_{\tilde{n}_2}(\eta) \text{ for } \eta \in (0, 1] \text{ and}$$

$$A_{c\tilde{n}_1}(\eta) = cA_{\tilde{n}_1}(\eta) \text{ for } \eta \in (0, 1].$$

Moreover, if $A_{\tilde{l}}(\eta) = l$ for $\eta \in (0, 1]$, then \tilde{l} is called the constant gradual real number."

Using the above operations on $\mathcal{G}(\mathbb{R})$ Sadeqi and Azari [10] defined the *GNLS* as follows :

Definition 1.2 "Let \mathcal{X} be a real vector space. The function $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}} : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{G}^*(\mathbb{R})$ is said to be a gradual norm on \mathcal{X} , if for every $\eta \in (0, 1]$, following three properties are satisfied for any $x, y \in \mathcal{X}$

(\mathcal{G}_1) $A_{\|x\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) = A_{\theta}(\eta)$ iff $x = \theta$, the zero vector of \mathcal{X} ;

(\mathcal{G}_2) $A_{\|\lambda x\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) = |\lambda|A_{\|x\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta)$ for any $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$;

(\mathcal{G}_3) $A_{\|x+y\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \leq A_{\|x\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) + A_{\|y\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta)$.

The pair $(\mathcal{X}, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}})$ is called a gradual normed linear space or briefly *GNLS*."

Let $\mathcal{X} = \mathbb{R}^n$, and $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $0 < \eta \leq 1$. If $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}}$ on \mathbb{R}^n is defined by

$$A_{\|x\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) = e^{\eta} \sum_{j=1}^n |x_j|$$

then Sadeqi and Azari [10] shown that $(\mathcal{X}, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}})$ is a *GNLS*.

"A sequence $w = (t_k)$ in *GNLS*: $(\mathcal{X}, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}})$ is said to be convergent to t_0 w.r.t the gradual norm $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}}$, if for every $\eta \in (0, 1]$ and $\epsilon > 0$, there exist $m \in \mathbb{N}$ s.t $A_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) < \epsilon, \forall k \geq m$. In this case, we write $\mathcal{G} - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} t_k = t_0$."

"A sequence $t = (t_k)$ in *GNLS*: $(\mathcal{X}, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}})$ is said to be Cauchy w.r.t gradual norm $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}}$, if for every $\eta \in (0, 1]$ and $\epsilon > 0$, there exists $m_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ s.t $A_{\|t_k - t_m\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) < \epsilon, \forall k, m \geq m_0$."

Choudhury and Debnath [1] defined \mathcal{I} -statistical convergence in *GNLS* and studied some interesting relations with other methods of summability.

Definition 1.2 “A sequence $t = (t_k)$ in $(\mathcal{X}, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}})$ is $S(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$ -summable to t_0 w.r.t $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}}$ provided for $\epsilon > 0, 0 < \delta \leq 1, \eta > 0$

$$\left\{ r \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{n} \left| \{k \leq n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\} \right| \geq \delta \right\} \in \mathcal{I};$$

denoted by $S(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G}) - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} t_k = t_0$ or simply $t_k \rightarrow t_0$ ($S(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$) as $k \rightarrow \infty$.”

$$\text{Let } [S(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})] = \left\{ t = (t_k) \in \mathcal{X} : S(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G}) - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} t_k \text{ exists} \right\}.$$

In present paper, we introduce two methods of summability: $S_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$ -summability and $V_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$ -summability in *GNLSs*. We obtain some interesting inclusion relations among these summability methods in *GNLS*.

2 $S_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$ and $V_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$ -summability

Throughout the work, unless otherwise stated, \mathcal{I} will be an admissible ideal and $(\mathcal{X}, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}})$ be a *GNLS*.

Definition 2.1 A sequence $t = (t_k)$ in $(\mathcal{X}, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}})$ is said to be $S_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$ -summable to t_0 w.r.t $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}}$ if for $\epsilon > 0, 0 < \delta \leq 1$ and $\eta > 0$

$$\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \{k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\} \right| \geq \delta \right\} \in \mathcal{I};$$

denoted by $S_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G}) - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} t_k = t_0$ or simply $t_k \rightarrow t_0$ ($S_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$) as $k \rightarrow \infty$.

$$\text{Let } [S_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})] = \left\{ t = (t_k) \in \mathcal{X} : S_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G}) - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} t_k \text{ exists} \right\}.$$

Definition 2.2 A sequence $t = (t_k)$ in $(\mathcal{X}, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}})$ is $V_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$ -summable to t_0 w.r.t $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}}$ if for $\epsilon > 0$ and $\eta > 0$

$$\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \sum_{k \in I_n} \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon \right\} \in \mathcal{I};$$

denoted by, $V_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G}) - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} t_k = t_0$ or simply $t_k \rightarrow t_0$ ($V_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$) as $k \rightarrow \infty$.

$$\text{Let } [V_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})] = \left\{ t = (t_k) \in \mathcal{X} : V_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G}) - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} t_k \text{ exists} \right\}$$

Example 2.3 Let $\mathcal{I}_f = \{A \subseteq \mathbb{N}, A \text{ is a finite}\}$, $\mathcal{X} = \mathbb{R}^m$ and $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}} : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow G^*$ defined by

$$\mathcal{A}_{\|t\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) = e^\eta \sum_{i=1}^m |t_i|$$

where $t = (t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m) \in \mathcal{X}$ and $0 < \eta \leq 1$. Then $(\mathbb{R}^m, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}})$ is a *GNLS*. We now define a sequence $t = (t_k)$ by

$$t_k = \begin{cases} (0, 0, \dots, m) & \text{if } k \in J_n, J_n = [n - \lfloor \sqrt{\lambda_n} \rfloor + 1, n] \\ (0, 0, \dots, 0) = \theta & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

then for $\epsilon > 0$ and $0 < \eta \leq 1$

$$\begin{aligned} K(\epsilon, \eta) &= \{k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\} = \{k \in I_n : e^\eta \sum_{i=1}^m |t_i| \geq \epsilon\} \\ &= \{k \in I_n : t_k = (0, 0, \dots, m)\} \\ &= \{k \in I_n : k \in J_n\} \end{aligned}$$

and therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| K(\epsilon, \eta) \right|_c &\leq \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \{k \in I_n : k \in J_n\} \right|_c \\ &\leq \frac{\sqrt{\lambda_n}}{\lambda_n} \rightarrow 0. \end{aligned}$$

This gives for $\delta > 0$,

$$\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \{k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - \theta\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\} \right|_c \geq \delta \right\} \in \mathcal{I}_f$$

as it is a finite set and therefore $S_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G}) - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} t_k = \theta$.

In the next theorem we establish relationships between the spaces $[S_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})]$, $[V_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})]$ and $l_\infty(\mathcal{G})$, where $l_\infty(\mathcal{G})$ denotes the space of bounded sequences in \mathcal{X} w.r.t. $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}}$.

Theorem 2.4 For any sequence $t = (t_k)$ in \mathcal{X} , we have the following.

- (i) $[V_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})] \subset [S_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})]$ and the inclusion is proper.
- (ii) In addition, if $t = (t_k)$ is bounded in \mathcal{X} w.r.t. the gradual norm $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $t_k \rightarrow t_0$ ($S_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$), then $t_k \rightarrow t_0$ ($V_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$), i.e., $[S_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})] \subseteq [V_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})]$.
- (iii) $[S_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})] \cap l_\infty(\mathcal{G}) = [V_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})] \cap l_\infty(\mathcal{G})$.

Proof. (i) We assume that $t = (t_k)$ in \mathcal{X} be s.t $t_k \rightarrow t_0$ ($V_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$). Then for $\epsilon > 0$ and $\eta > 0$

$$\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \sum_{k \in I_n} \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon \right\} \in \mathcal{I} \tag{1}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k \in I_n} \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) &= \sum_{\substack{k \in I_n \\ \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon}} \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) + \sum_{\substack{k \in I_n \\ \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) < \epsilon}} \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \\ &\geq \sum_{\substack{k \in I_n \\ \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon}} \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \\ &\geq \epsilon \cdot \left| \{k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\} \right|_c. \end{aligned}$$

So for each $\delta > 0$

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \{k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\} \right|_c \geq \delta \text{ implies } \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \sum_{k \in I_n} \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\delta = \epsilon_1$$

and so

$$\begin{aligned} &\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \{k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\} \right|_c \geq \delta \right\} \\ &\subseteq \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \sum_{k \in I_n} \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon_1 \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

By (1), the later set is in \mathcal{I} , which implies the former set is also in \mathcal{I} and therefore $t_k \rightarrow t_0$ ($S_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$) as $k \rightarrow \infty$.

For proper inclusion, consider the sequence $t = (t_k)$ in \mathbb{R}^m as in Example 2.3. Clearly it is an unbounded sequence w.r.t $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $t_k \rightarrow \theta$ ($S_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$) as $k \rightarrow \infty$. Moreover

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_n} \sum_{k \in I_n} \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - \theta\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \not\rightarrow \theta, \tag{2}$$

and therefore $N_\phi(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G}) - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} t_k \neq \theta$.

(ii) Let $t = (t_k)$ is bounded w.r.t. $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}}$ and $t_k \rightarrow t_0$ ($S_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$). Let $M > 0$ s.t for for all k , $0 < \eta \leq 1$

$$\mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - \theta\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \leq M \tag{3}$$

and for $\epsilon > 0$, $\delta > 0$

$$\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \{k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\} \right|_c \geq \delta \right\} \in \mathcal{I}. \tag{4}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now, } \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \sum_{k \in I_n} \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) &= \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \sum_{\substack{k \in I_n \\ \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \frac{\epsilon}{2}}} \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) + \\ &\quad \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \sum_{\substack{k \in I_n \\ \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) < \frac{\epsilon}{2}}} \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \\ &\leq \frac{M}{\lambda_n} \left| \{k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \frac{\epsilon}{2}\} \right|_c + \frac{\epsilon}{2} \end{aligned}$$

and so

$$\begin{aligned} &\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \sum_{k \in I_n} \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon \right\} \\ &\subseteq \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \{k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\} \right|_c \geq \frac{\epsilon}{2M} \right\} \in \mathcal{I} \\ &\quad \left(\text{by (4) for } \delta = \frac{\epsilon}{2M} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Consequently

$$\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \sum_{k \in I_n} \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon \right\} \in \mathcal{I}$$

and therefore we have $t_k \rightarrow t_0$ ($V_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$) as $k \rightarrow \infty$.

(iii) This is a direct implication of (i) and (ii).

Theorem 2.5 $[S(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})] \subseteq [S_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})]$ if $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda_n}{n} > 0$.

Proof. Let $t = (t_k) \in [S(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})]$ s.t $t_k \rightarrow t_0$ ($S(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$) and $\liminf_{r \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda_n}{n} > 0$. Let $0 < \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda_n}{n} = \alpha$, then by definition the set $\{n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{\lambda_n}{n} < \frac{\alpha}{2}\}$ is a finite set.

Now for $\epsilon > 0$ and $0 < \eta \leq 1$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{n} |\{k \leq n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\}|_c &\geq \frac{1}{n} |\{k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\}|_c \\ &= \frac{\lambda_n}{n} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_n} |\{k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\}|_c \right). \end{aligned}$$

\implies for $\delta > 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} &\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} |\{k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\}|_c \geq \delta \right\} \\ \subseteq &\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{n} |\{k \leq n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\}|_c \geq \frac{\alpha \delta}{2} \right\} \cup \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{\lambda_n}{n} < \frac{\alpha}{2} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Since $t_k \rightarrow t_0$ ($S(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$), and \mathcal{I} is an admissible ideal so the later set is in \mathcal{I} and therefore by second property of an ideal \mathcal{I} , the former set belongs to \mathcal{I} . Hence, $t_k \rightarrow t_0$ ($S_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$) i.e., $t = (t_k) \in [S_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})]$.

Theorem 2.6 $[S_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})] \subseteq [S(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})]$ provided that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda_n}{n} = 1$.

Proof. Let $t = (t_k) \in [S_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})]$ s.t $t_k \rightarrow t_0$ ($S_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$) and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda_n}{n} = 1$, then for any $\delta > 0$ we can find $m_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $n \geq m_0$ we have

$$\left| \frac{\lambda_n}{n} - 1 \right| < \frac{\delta}{2}.$$

Now for $\epsilon > 0$, $0 < \eta \leq 1$ and $n \geq m_0$,

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{n} |\{k \leq n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\}|_c \\ = &\frac{1}{n} |\{k \leq n - \lambda_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\}|_c + \frac{1}{n} |\{k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\}|_c \\ &\leq \left(\frac{n - \lambda_n}{n} \right) + \frac{1}{n} |\{k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\}|_c \\ &\leq 1 - \left(1 - \frac{\delta}{2} \right) + \frac{1}{n} |\{k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\}|_c \\ &= \frac{\delta}{2} + \frac{1}{n} |\{k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\}|_c. \end{aligned}$$

This implies that we have the containment

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\{ r \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{n} \left| \{ k \leq n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon \} \right|_c \geq \delta \right\} \\ \subseteq & \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{n} \left| \{ k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_0\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon \} \right|_c \geq \frac{\delta}{2} \right\} \cup \{1, 2, \dots, m_0\}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $\{1, 2, \dots, m_0\}$ is finite and $t_k \rightarrow t_0$ ($S_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$) so the latter union belongs to \mathcal{I} which immediately gives the former set in \mathcal{I} . This shows that $t_k \rightarrow t_0$ ($S(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$).

Theorem 2.7 If the space $(\mathcal{X}, \|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{G}})$ is complete, then $[S_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})] \cap l_{\infty}(\mathcal{G})$ is a closed space.

Proof. To prove the closedness of the space $[S_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})] \cap l_{\infty}(\mathcal{G})$, consider a sequence $(t^n), n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ in $[S_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})] \cap l_{\infty}(\mathcal{G})$ s.t $t^n \rightarrow t$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. We shall show that $t \in [S_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})] \cap l_{\infty}(\mathcal{G})$.

As for each $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, (t^n) \in [S_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})]$, so let $t^n \rightarrow p_n$ ($S_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$) for $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Let (ϵ_n) where $\epsilon_n = \frac{\epsilon}{2^n}$ be a decreasing sequence with $\epsilon_n \rightarrow 0$. Since $t^n \rightarrow t$, so, let $n \in \mathbb{N}$ s.t

$$\sup \mathcal{A}_{\|t^n - t\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) < \frac{\epsilon_n}{4} \tag{5}$$

For $0 < \delta < 1$, if we define

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \{ k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k^n - p_n\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \frac{\epsilon_n}{4} \} \right|_c < \frac{\delta}{3} \right\} \quad \text{and} \\ B &= \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \{ k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k^{n+1} - p_{n+1}\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \frac{\epsilon_{n+1}}{4} \} \right|_c < \frac{\delta}{3} \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

then $A, B \in \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{I})$, which gives $\emptyset \neq A \cap B$. Let $n \in A \cap B$, then

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \{ k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k^n - p_n\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \frac{\epsilon_n}{4} \} \right|_c < \frac{\delta}{3} \\ & \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \{ k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k^{n+1} - p_{n+1}\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \frac{\epsilon_{n+1}}{4} \} \right|_c < \frac{\delta}{3} \end{aligned}$$

and therefore we have

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \left\{ k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k^n - p_n\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \frac{\epsilon_n}{4} \vee \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k^{n+1} - p_{n+1}\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \frac{\epsilon_{n+1}}{4} \right\} \right|_c < \delta < 1.$$

This shows $\exists k \in I_n$ s.t

$$\mathcal{A}_{\|t_k^n - p_n\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) < \frac{\epsilon_n}{4} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k^{n+1} - p_{n+1}\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) < \frac{\epsilon_{n+1}}{4}. \quad (6)$$

Now, we can write

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}_{\|p_n - p_{n+1}\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) &\leq \mathcal{A}_{\|p_n - t_k^n\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) + \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k^n - t_k^{n+1}\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) + \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k^{n+1} - p_{n+1}\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \\ &\leq \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k^n - p_n\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) + \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k^{n+1} - p_{n+1}\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) + \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k^n - t_k^{n+1}\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \\ &\leq \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k^n - p_n\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) + \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k^{n+1} - p_{n+1}\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \\ &\quad + \sup \mathcal{A}_{\|t^n - t\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) + \sup \mathcal{A}_{\|t^{n+1} - t\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \\ &\leq \frac{\epsilon_n}{4} + \frac{\epsilon_{n+1}}{4} + \frac{\epsilon_n}{4} + \frac{\epsilon_{n+1}}{4} \\ &\leq \epsilon_n. \end{aligned}$$

This shows that $(p_n : n \in \mathbb{N})$ is Cauchy in \mathcal{X} , therefore is convergent in \mathcal{X} . Let $p_n \rightarrow p$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. We will show that $t = (t_k) \rightarrow p$ ($S_{\lambda}(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G})$). Let $\epsilon > 0$ be given. Take $n \in \mathbb{N}$ s.t. $\epsilon_n < \frac{\epsilon}{4}$, $\sup \mathcal{A}_{\|t^n - t\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) < \frac{\epsilon}{4}$ and $\mathcal{A}_{\|p_n - p\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) < \frac{\epsilon}{4}$. Now we can write

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \left\{ k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - p\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon \right\} \right|_c \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \left\{ k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k^n - p_n\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) + \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - t_k^n\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) + \mathcal{A}_{\|p_n - p\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon \right\} \right|_c \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \left\{ k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k^n - p_n\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) + \frac{\epsilon}{4} + \frac{\epsilon}{4} \geq \epsilon \right\} \right|_c \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \left\{ k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k^n - p_n\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq +\frac{\epsilon}{2} \right\} \right|_c \end{aligned}$$

and therefore we have the containment

$$\begin{aligned} &\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \left\{ k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k^n - p_n\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq +\frac{\epsilon}{2} \right\} \right|_c < \delta \right\} \\ &\subseteq \left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \left\{ k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - p\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon \right\} \right|_c < \delta \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Since the former set belongs to $\in \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{I})$ and therefore the later set belongs to $\in \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{I})$. i.e.,

$$\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} \left| \left\{ k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - p\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon \right\} \right|_c < \delta \right\} \in \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{I})$$

which immediately gives

$$\left\{ n \in \mathbb{N} : \frac{1}{\lambda_n} |\{k \in I_n : \mathcal{A}_{\|t_k - p\|_{\mathcal{G}}}(\eta) \geq \epsilon\}|_c \geq \delta \right\} \in \mathcal{I}.$$

This implies that $t = (t_k) \rightarrow p (S_\lambda(\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{G}))$ and the proof of the theorem is complete.

3 Conflict of interest

The author has no conflict of interest.

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